

The relationship between Odd perfect numbers and Mason Primes

HuangShan

(Wuhu Institute of Technology, China, Wuhu, 241003)

Abstract: Associate the sum of the powers of multiple primes with complete numbers.

Key words: perfect numbers, Odd perfect numbers, the sum of the powers of primes ,Mason primes.

Proving that there is no odd perfect number is simple, similar to the process of negating the Euler product formula.

$\forall m, n, k, d, d_q, n_k \in \mathbb{N}, \forall p, p_k, p_q \in \text{prime numbers}$.

Divisor of $\forall p^n$, Such as, $p^0, p^1, p^2, p^3, p^4, \dots, p^n$, Sum of divisors of $\forall p^n$, $S_n = \sum_{m=0}^n p^m = \frac{p^{n+1}-p^0}{p^1-1}$.

So, **Sum of divisors of $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$** , $S_{\prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}} = \prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1}-p_k^0}{p_k-1}$,

If , $\frac{S_{\prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}}}{\prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}} = 2$, $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$ is called a perfect number.

That is, $\prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1}-p_k^0}{(p_k-1)p_k^{n_k}} = 2$, $\prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1}-p_k^0}{p_k-1} = 2 \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$,

Solve this equation ,If and only if $2^{d+1} - 2^0 = p$, $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k} = 2^d * p$ Have positive integer solution,

While $2^d * p$ is an even number, so there is no odd perfect number.

We know from Mason primes that when $2^{d+1} - 2^0 = p$, $d + 1$ must be a prime.

So, extend further, if there is, $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1}-p_k^0}{p_k-1} = p_q \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$,

To solve this equation, there is if and only if $\frac{p_q^{d_q+1}-p_q^0}{p_q-1} = p$, $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k} = p_q^{d_q} * p$ has a positive integer solution.

So, if we compare Mason primes, whether $d_q + 1$ is a prime when $\frac{p_q^{d_q+1}-p_q^0}{p_q-1} = p$.

How do you prove it? If this corollary holds, it can be deduced that $p_q^{d_q+1} = p(p_q - 1) + 1$.

By solving this equation, it is found that if p_q and p are arbitrary primes.

Then, the condition that $d_q + 1$ is a positive integer is that $d_q + 1$ is a prime.

Reference: none.